

Eight Treasures Mountain (Babaoshan) Revolutionary Cemetery

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Entry tags: Chinese State Religion, Religious Group, Communism, China, Beijing, Cemetery, Secularism, Religious Place, Chinese Religion, Martyrs, Martyry

In 1950, the People's Republic of China (PRC) began transforming the Eight Treasures Mountain (Babaoshan) into a national cemetery for its most esteemed members and supporters. Although the PRC erases the imperial and republican past, it follows its predecessors in shaping national memory by creating a sacred site for the loyal dead. Furthermore, despite atheist self-proclamation, the PRC relies on traditional beliefs and practices to memorialize its highest-ranking cadres and most devoted supporters. The state's attempts to shape national memory have not been without resistance from the bereaved families of those who died in controversial pasts. The PRC in the twenty-first century, turns to information technology and eco-burial methods to manage the growing population of the dead and to meet consumerist demands of its living population. When the CCP leaders removed all remnants of the imperial eunuchs from the Eight Treasures Mountain, they thought the land was sufficiently purified to hold the ashes of their most esteemed members. But the ghosts came later in the political mayhem of the Cultural Revolution and the Tiananmen Square crackdown, both of which shook the foundation of the Party and continue to rumble beneath the surface. Despite the state's efforts to control the narrative of history by dictating who can (and who must) reside in the deified Revolutionary Cemetery, the living persist in fighting for the memories of the dead.

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2024 CE

Region: Beijing

Region tags: China, East Asia

Beijing

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

— Source 1: Vu, Linh D. "Un)rest in revolution: Beijing's Eight Treasures Mountain (Babaoshan) Revolutionary Cemetery and the making of China's national memory." *Memory Studies*, 2024.

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– Source 2: Hung, Chang-tai. *Mao's New World: Political Culture in the Early People's Republic*. Ithaca: Cornell University Press, 2011.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <http://www.beijinglingyuan.com/lydq/1258.html>

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Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– No

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Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

– Other [specify]: The name “Eight Treasures” comes from the imperial era, when various types of clay, limestone, and sandstone were quarried in this area.

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Type of elevation

– Hill

Notes: While the site is called "mountain," it is only slightly elevated.

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Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

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Type of feature

- Clearing
- Trackway or road-surface
- Water feature
- Plantings

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Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

Yes

Notes: It is located in the western suburbs of Beijing. Yet as Beijing has been expanded, the cemetery is in a rather urbanized area.

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Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

No

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Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

Yes

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Is the place situated in a rural setting:

No

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Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– Yes

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Is there an established route of travel connecting it to a wider transportation network:

– Yes

Notes: The cemetery is a stop on on subway line 1 of Beijing. Line 1 goes through the very center of the capital with stops at Tian'anmen Square.

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Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

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A single structure

– No

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One single feature

– Mound

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↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

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↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: The site has many construction stages. During the Yuan dynasty (1279–1368), a Buddhist monk, built the Temple of Efficacious Prosperity (Lingfu si) to the south of the mountain. In the fifteenth century, the Temple of Extending Longevity (Yanshou si) was built in honor of General Gang Bing (? - c. 1411), who, according to legend, castrated himself to show his loyalty to the Yongle Emperor (r. 1402–1424). The temple estate provided a livelihood for retired eunuchs and served as their burial ground. The Temple of Extending Longevity was later expanded and renamed the Temple of Protecting Loyalty and Safeguarding the State (Baozhong huguo ci). Since religious and burial sites are usually chosen for efficacious and auspicious geomancy, the Japanese Army, the Nationalists, and the Communists successively took over the Eight Treasures Mountain area to honor their respective dead.

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↳ A group of features:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2023 CE

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↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

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↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

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↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Memorial

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↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

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↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

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↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Notes: More structures are added to host ashes.

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↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

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↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

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In antiquity

– More than once

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In modernity

– Renaissance

– Post-Renaissance

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Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– No

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Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

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Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Yes

Notes: for the worship of revolutionary ancestors (geming xianlie) of the Chinese Communist Party.

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Is it a cenotaph:

– No

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– Yes

Notes: It commemorates followers of the Chinese Communist Party.

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

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↳ Specify

– Private individual

– Other [specify]: Chinese Communist Party

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Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– No

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Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

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Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

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Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

Notes: The place was create when the People's Republic of China was founded in 1950.

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Specify

– War/battle

Notes: Months after the Chinese Civil War (1946-1949), the People's Republic of China (PRC) began transforming the Eight Treasures Mountain (Babaoshan) into a national cemetery for its highest-ranking cadres and most devoted supporters.

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

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Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Notes: The Chinese Communist Party (CCP) sponsored the space to bury high-ranking cadres.

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

–Other [specify]: Expression of devotion with expectation of securing political legitimacy.

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Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

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Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

Notes: A pair of stone lions on dragon-motif platforms guard the entrance. Buildings inside the cemetery are decorated with blue-painted columns and red-glazed tiles, characteristic of the traditional temples and of Republican-era aesthetic. The cemetery garden is adorned with pines and conifers, which traditionally symbolize loyalty and longevity. Previously built temples have been converted into columbaria.

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Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– No

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Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Notes: There were imperial-era and Republican-era temples and structures before the People's Republic of China took over and repurposed these buildings.

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Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

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Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

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Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

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↳ Earth

– No

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↳ Sand

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

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↳ Clay

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

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Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Plaster

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

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↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

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↳ Wood

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

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↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Grass

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

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↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Stone

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Metal

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Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Cement

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Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

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↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

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↳ On the outside:

– Yes

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↳ On the inside:

– Yes

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↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– No

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↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– No

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↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– No

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↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

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↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

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↳ Cult statues:

– No

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↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– No

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↳ Statues of humans:

– Yes

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↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Busts on gravestones

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↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures

project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– I don't know

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↳ Are there paintings present:

– I don't know

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↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

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↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

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↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– No

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↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative

[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

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↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

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↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Inscriptions of names on tombstones

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↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

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Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

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Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Notes: This is where the ashes of high-ranking Communist Party members are laid to rest in columbaria and where bereaved families make ritual offerings to their loved ones.

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Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– Yes

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↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s):

– Yes

Notes: Besides Communist cadres, some Qing royal members were buried here.

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↳ For the worship of a deified human:

– No

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↳ For the worship of a deceased hero:

– Yes

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Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– Yes

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↳ Cremation:

– Yes

Notes: In the 1950s, Mao Zedong launched a nationwide campaign to promote cremation in order to preserve land for agriculture. The Eight Treasures Mountain was the first place to offer cremation services in Beijing, serving both party and non-party members.

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↳ **Mummification:**

– No

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↳ **Interment:**

– Yes

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↳ **Cannibalism:**

– No

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↳ **Exposure to the elements:**

– No

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↳ **Feeding to animals:**

– No

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↳ **Secondary burial:**

– Yes

Notes: Some bodies were exhumed and reburied at the Eight Treasures Mountain.

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

↳ Other intensive (time/resources expended) treatment [Specify]:

–Other [specify]: ecological burials

Notes: In order to meet the demand for space, the Eight Treasures Mountain cemetery authorities pioneer eco-burial approaches. It is reported that there are seven new burial methods at the Eight Treasures Mountain. For a stone burial, the name, birthdate, and death date of the deceased are engraved on a small stone slab with the ashes buried underneath. For a wall burial, the ashes are deposited in an enclosed columbarium. For a scattered ashes burial, the ashes are placed in a biodegradable urn and buried three feet deep to allow the remains to completely decompose. For a flowerbed burial, the ashes are marked with a ring of flower shrubs instead of a tombstone. For a water burial, the ashes are buried near an artificial pond and integrated into the landscape. For a tree burial, the ashes are buried around a tree and marked with rocks. For a lawn burial, the ashes are buried underneath a large lawn and marked with small headstones that disappear into the grass. These new forms of burial allow the cemetery to host an increasingly large number of ashes while creating a garden-like environment for the living.

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Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: The site has been used for burials as early as the 15th century.

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Eco-burials

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Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Notes: But the cemetery ground as the place where “the red resources are the most abundant, the most concentrated, the richest, and the most archetypal” and that the living should collect this “precious spiritual wealth,” that is, the revolutionary spirit.

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

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Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2023 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2023 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2023 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2023 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2023 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2023 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: The general population, including elementary and middle school students, are regularly organized to attend the Red Grave Sweeping Festival where they are taught about the sacrifice of revolutionaries.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2023 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: Relatives of the dead make offerings during the death anniversaries.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2023 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: Hundreds or thousands.

Notes: In an occasion of the funeral of the former premier Zhao Ziyang (1919-2005), who the use of force against the Tiananmen protesters and was placed under house arrest for the rest of his life, over 3,000 people made it to the event.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2023 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: During the annual Tomb-sweeping Festival, when an important figure is buried, commemoration of important political events

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2023 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2023 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2023 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2023 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2023 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2023 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2023 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

Notes: Offerings include flower wreaths and other funerary goods such as incenses and paper money.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2023 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are material offerings mandatory:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2023 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2023 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2023 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2023 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2023 CE

Status of Participants: Elite Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2023 CE

Status of Participants: Elite Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ By all the community

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2023 CE

Status of Participants: Elite Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ By specific individuals

– Yes [specify]: Politicians

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2023 CE

Status of Participants: Elite Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2023 CE

Status of Participants: Elite Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2023 CE

Status of Participants: Elite Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2023 CE

Status of Participants: Elite Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2023 CE

Status of Participants: Elite Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2023 CE

Status of Participants: Elite Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2023 CE

Status of Participants: Elite Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: But school students and other social groups make regular visits as part of their learning and emulating these revolutionaries buried here.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2023 CE

Status of Participants: Elite Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

–optional (common)

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– No

Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– No

Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2023 CE

Status of Participants: Elite Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are festivals present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2023 CE

Status of Participants: Elite Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Frequency of festivals

– specify: Qingming (Tomb-sweeping) Festival in the spring

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2023 CE

Status of Participants: Elite Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– Elites

– Non-elites

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2023 CE

Status of Participants: Elite Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2023 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Requires special maintenance/cleansing of the place:

– Yes

Notes: Because of the large number of people whose ashes are hosted there, the Office of Cemetery Management and Technological Advancement at the Eight Treasures Mountain Revolutionary Cemetery has designed new features for tombstones that allow them to protrude and retract from the ground using waterproof and dustproof hydraulic mechanisms. As of 2021, family members of the deceased can lift the cover from the lawn and press the unlock button, upon which a tombstone slowly rises for them to perform the ceremony of sweeping the gravestones. When the service is complete, they can press the lock button to retract the headstone and close the cover, restoring the lawn to its flat surface. Family members can also scan a QR code on each headstone to view a portrait of the deceased and read about their lineage—information that does not fit on a small tombstone.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2023 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Requires new construction/decoration of the place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2023 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Requires maintenance/replacement of cult statue(s):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2023 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:

– number: Hundreds

Notes: On the occasion of an important politician's funeral, thousands of people attend. Family members are allowed to visit the graves or niches and perform worship. However, in case of controversial figures, access may be limited by the government.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2023 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2023 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2023 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2023 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– No

Notes: While there are no religious specialists, there are Communist cadres educated on the site's history and significance. They give lectures to student groups and other visitors.

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Notes: There is an education center to train cadres who provide lectures to the general population.

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

Notes: The site provides cremation and funeral services to those who are qualified. Parts of the cemetery are open to the public. Students and other groups can visit for lessons on the Communist revolutionary spirit. Visitors interested in the history of the Chinese Communist Party can also gain entrance to certain areas. With the rise of "red tourism," visits to sites of historical significance to the Chinese Communist Party educate Chinese citizens today about the Communist heroic past and fuel their patriotic sentiments. Such visits are also opportunities to enjoy the touristic experience, which includes sightseeing, consuming food and services. The Eight Treasures Mountain is intended to provide not only revolutionary lessons but also leisurely occasions within the consumer-driven urban environment. The graves are made to disappear into the landscape so that the living can enjoy the scenery.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– No

Notes: But people can gather here to protest certain rulings.

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Function for water management:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– Yes

Notes: The site is a stop on a subway line.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Funeral products are sold here.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Notes: Writings and exhibits on the Chinese Communist Party are stored onsite.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2023 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Eight Treasures Mountain (Babaoshan) Revolutionary Cemetery, Cheater, A. P.. "Death Ritual as Political Trickster in the People's Republic of China" 26 (July 1991). <https://doi.org/10.2307/2949869>.

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